

STUDIES OF TRANSVERSE IMPACT DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS USING A
HOPKINSON TYPE PRESSURE-BAR TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Previous work on the transverse impact testing of fibre-reinforced plastics is briefly reviewed. A new apparatus, using a Hopkinson type instrumented input bar, is described and results presented for low-velocity impacts on plain-weave reinforced epoxy laminates with either all-carbon plies or a hybrid combination of carbon plies and glass plies. Distinct differences are observed in the damage mechanisms for the two types of specimen.

INTRODUCTION

Most early work on the impact resistance of fibre-reinforced composites, probably for reasons of experimental simplicity, used versions of the Izod [1] or Charpy [2] impact bend tests. These allow a qualitative comparison between different materials of the energy required to cause fracture for this particular loading arrangement but neither provides any fundamental data nor models the type of impact observed in practice. Attempts to obtain more basic data on the material behaviour of fibre-reinforced composites under impact loading have generally used versions of the split Hopkinson's pressure bar apparatus, in compression [3,4], in torsion [5,6] and more recently also in tension [7,8]. Such studies have shown significant increases in the modulus, failure strength and strain to fracture for glass-fibre reinforced composites under impact loading but rather smaller effects of loading rate on carbon-fibre reinforced materials [8].

Other investigators have developed drop-weight testing techniques in attempts to simulate the transverse impact loading often observed in practice. From such tests data on the structural, rather than material, response might be obtained. Beaumont et al. [9] observed the damage resulting in fuselage skin materials after impact at different velocities. The results obtained were qualitative and no attempt was made to measure the loads applied during the impact process. In many subsequent investigations, however, instrumented drop-weight impact tests were developed. Broutman and Rotem [10], for example, impacted beam specimens at centre span, the ends being supported on load cells, while a high-speed camera was used to observe the deformation. For GFRP specimens they found increased strength and energy absorption at high rates of loading and observed that the mechanism of energy

absorption was by delamination between layers and between fibres and could, therefore, be affected by the surface treatment of the fibres and the surface characteristics of the laminae.

More commonly the load cell, often a piezo-electric force transducer, was attached directly to the falling weight [11,12,13,14] and the resulting force-time curve used to obtain energy, velocity and displacement as functions of time and force as a function of displacement. This requires the assumption of quasi-static equilibrium within the specimen. In many cases oscillations were observed on the force-time signals obtained from the load cell, even though filtering techniques were used to smooth the data [11,13], an indication of stress wave reflection within the load cell as well as the specimen. Despite these oscillations, however, Elber [15] has shown that for impact velocities up to 7m/s the assumption of quasi-static equilibrium in the specimen may not be unreasonable, although a detailed examination of the resulting damage showed differences between that caused by impact loading, where fibre failure was greater in plies close to the back surface, and that caused by quasi-static loading, where fibre failure was greatest nearer the centre plies. Residual damage in CFRP panels was also studied by Dorey and Sidey [16] after impact at a wide range of velocities. Below 60m/s simple bending theory and the assumption of quasi-static conditions in the specimen could be used to predict the critical incident energy to give failure. Above 80m/s a relatively clean hole was punched in the specimen, which could be treated as effectively rigid during the period of loading. It was in the intermediate range of velocity, from 60 to 80m/s, where stress wave reflections within the specimen clearly affected the mechanical response, that the most marked drop in residual strength was observed.

In the light of these earlier investigations the present study seeks to develop an improved transverse impact test for composite laminates in which a Hopkinson type pressure-bar is used in an attempt to obtain an unambiguous measure of force, velocity and displacement without the need to assume conditions of quasi-static equilibrium, and in which the importance of stress wave reflections within the specimen may be determined for any chosen geometry. The testing technique will then be used to study the development of impact damage in woven hybrid carbon/glass laminates under well-defined loading conditions.

MATERIALS

Two laminated composite plates, each 0.33m square, hand laid up using Ciba-Geigy XD925 epoxy resin, were supplied by Fothergill and Harvey Ltd. The first plate contained 13 plain-weave carbon mats and had a 50% fibre content by weight. The second plate contained a total of 6 plain-weave carbon plies and 20 plain-weave glass plies, also with a 50% fibre content by weight and a lay up sequence of (CGGGCGGGGCGG)_s. Both plates had a thickness of 3.6mm. The carbon fabric, designated A002/000, was woven from Toray 3000 filament fibre tows, type T300-3000A, and had a weight of 189g/m² and an approximate thickness of 0.28mm. This fabric has a relatively coarse weave, with only 47 ends and picks per 10cm. The glass fabric, designated Y0314/205, was woven from continuous E-glass fibre tows type 11X2EC5 and had a weight of 79g/m² and an approximate thickness of 0.08mm. With 177 ends and 173 picks per 10cm the weave was much finer than for the carbon fabric. Both laminates were C-scanned before testing and no flaws were detected.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Impact tests were carried out using a modified Hopkinson-bar technique. The test rig and the related Lagrange (x,t) diagram are shown schematically in fig.1. A projectile is fired from a small air gun and makes axial impact on the instrumented input bar. In principle it is possible, by varying the impact velocity, V , and the length of the projectile to control the magnitude and duration of the force applied to the specimen, a circular plate fully clamped at the edges and with an exposed area of 60mm diameter. In the present work the projectile and input bars have lengths of 0.33 and 0.99m respectively and both are machined from 12.5mm diameter steel bars. The end of the input bar in contact with the composite plate is hemispherical.

Signals from strain gauge stations I and II on the input bar were stored in a Datalabs type 912 transient recorder and subsequently transferred to an IBM PC microcomputer. A program has been developed which uses one dimensional elastic wave theory, as in the standard Hopkinson-bar test, to derive from this data the load, velocity and displacement at the centre of the specimen. Typical records from strain gauge stations I and II are seen in fig. 2a, for a test on an all-carbon laminate at a gas-gun firing pressure of 30 psi, corresponding to an impact velocity of $\sim 2\text{m/s}$. From these records the stress and velocity at the interface between the input bar and the centre of the composite specimen may be computed. To obtain the displacement at this point the velocity-time curve is numerically integrated, giving the displacement-time curve shown in fig.2b. It is clear that with the particular loading arrangement used here several reflections occur within the input bar before the peak displacement is attained. The corresponding variation of force with time at the centre of the specimen is shown in fig.2c. The high frequency noise which obscures this curve follows, in the main, from the extreme sensitivity of the Hopkinson type calculation of stress in the input bar to very small variations in the computed incident and reflected stress waves, although the effect of stress wave reflections within the specimen could also play a part.

Fig.1 Schematic View of Impact Apparatus and Related Lagrange (x,t) Diagram

Fig.2 Test Records for All-Carbon Specimen
 (Gas-gun pressure: 30psi)

To monitor wave effects within the specimen strain gauges were also fixed directly to the back surface of the specimen, in the positions shown in fig.3. In a few cases strain gauges were also fixed at the centre of the back of the specimen. This, however, was the point where impact damage was greatest and gauges placed here often became detached early in the test. Signals from such gauges were also stored in two further type 912 transient recorders, the signal from gauge station F being shown in fig.2d for the same test. It is clear that the stepped displacement curve, fig.2b, is closely mirrored by the strain gauge output from gauge station F, fig.2d, suggesting that this represents the overall equilibrium response of the specimen. However, the strain gauge signal also shows small superimposed oscillations which could indicate wave effects within the specimen. The first strain reduction in fig.2d is seen some $30\mu\text{s}$ after the start of the signal and would correspond to a shear wave reflected from the clamped edge of the specimen so it had travelled $\sim 20\text{mm}$, giving a shear wave speed of $\sim 670\text{m/s}$ and a through thickness shear modulus of $\sim 0.6\text{GPa}$, which is of the right order.

Assuming that, apart from these oscillations, the strain gauge signal in fig.2d represents the equilibrium response of the specimen, a quasi-static calibration curve may be obtained by determining the gauge signal for known central loads statically applied to the specimen. A linear calibration obtained in this way for gauge station F and an all-carbon specimen gives an alternative force-time curve which, see fig.2c, agrees well with the general shape of that derived from the Hopkinson bar analysis. Using this alternative estimate of force and the displacement-time curve of fig.2b, a force-displacement curve for the test may be derived, see fig.4. This shows large variations in stress, due to the stepped nature of the applied loading and to wave effects in the specimen, but does show the general form of the loading curve, in particular a peak load of $\sim 2.6\text{kN}$ and a maximum displacement of $\sim 1.2\text{mm}$ in a time of $\sim 1\text{ms}$.

The impacted specimens were C-scanned to determine the area of delamination. To assess the extent of fibre damage due to impact a thermal deplying technique was employed. The impacted laminate was held between two sheets of 2mm thick aluminium alloy to maintain flatness and then wrapped in two layers of aluminium foil to obtain an essentially inert environment. The assembly was then put into a pre-heated laboratory oven at 300°C for two hours and then allowed to cool in the oven overnight. The laminate was separated into individual plies, using a scalpel to assist in the deplying process. An 18.5mm wide strip was cut from the centre of each ply, the edge of the strip lying parallel to a weave direction, the strip including the region in which fibre damage was most expected. Tensile specimens were prepared by bonding the strip to aluminium end tabs using Chemlok type 304 epoxy adhesive and curing at room temperature overnight. The specimen gauge length was 25mm. Tests were performed in a standard Instron loading machine and the maximum quasi-static tensile load for each strip specimen was determined.

Fig.3 Strain Gauge Stations on Specimen back surface

RESULTS

Tests were performed on both the all-carbon and the hybrid carbon/glass laminates at gas-gun firing pressures of 30, 40 and 60psi, corresponding to impact velocities of ~ 2 , ~ 6 and ~ 8.3 m/s, on the all-carbon specimens and 40 and 60psi on the hybrid specimens. After testing each specimen was C-scanned to assess the maximum area of delamination and then subsequently depled to determine the residual strength of the various plies and find where the most fibre damage had occurred. Further tests are planned in which the specimens will be examined after testing using optical microscopy to study the fracture processes but this part of the programme is not yet complete and will not be reported on here.

Using the quasi-static load calibration for gauge station F maximum loads for tests on the all-carbon specimens of 4.3kN (at 40psi) and 5.5kN (at 60psi) were estimated. These estimates are only approximate since the quasi-static calibration strictly only applies while the specimen remains undamaged. Similar estimates are not available for the hybrid specimens since a quasi-static calibration has not yet been performed for this material. Maximum displacements, however, may be determined from the displacement-time curves obtained in all tests. Values so derived were 1.8 and 2.9mm, for all-carbon specimens at 40 and 60psi respectively and 1.23 and 2.9mm for the hybrid specimens at the same pressures. It should be noted, however, that in both tests at 60psi the displacement was still increasing when the analysis was terminated, i.e. at $\sim 1650\mu$ s, see fig.2b, whereas for the hybrid specimens at 40psi the displacement had returned to zero by the end of the calculation.

Results of the C-scans are shown in figs.5 and 6 for the three all-carbon and the two hybrid specimens respectively. No delamination was visible in the all-carbon specimen at 30psi. At 40psi, however, a significant delaminated region was seen, of approximately circular shape reflecting the planar isotropy of the reinforcement geometry, while at 60psi there was a similar, but increased, area of delamination. In contrast, the hybrid specimens showed a significantly smaller delaminated area at 40psi and a much larger one at 60psi.

Residual tensile strengths of individual plies in the various specimens after testing, determined as described above, were normalised by dividing by the average tensile strength, determined in the same way, for all the carbon and all the glass plies in an untested hybrid specimen. Normalised residual ply tensile strengths for the all-carbon specimens are shown in fig.7a and the hybrid specimens, including the untested specimen, in fig.7b. An indication of the experimental scatter, 0.94 to 1.08, may be seen in the results for the untested specimen. A markedly different behaviour is apparent for the all-carbon and the hybrid specimens. Thus, while at 30psi little fibre damage was seen in the all-carbon specimen, at 40psi only a few plies near the centre, plies 4 to 8, retained almost their undamaged strength, while at 60psi all plies showed a reduced strength, the least damaged, ply 5, having a relative strength of 0.75 and the most damaged, plies 12 and 13, relative strengths as low as 0.1. In contrast, for all but the surface plies, no significant fibre damage was seen in the hybrid specimens both at 40 and 60psi. Only the (carbon) back surface ply showed reduced strength at 40psi (relative value ~ 0.6). At 60psi both front and back surface plies were affected, relative strengths being ~ 0.3 and ~ 0.1 respectively, while several intermediate plies, carbon plies 6 and 16 and glass ply 15, showed strength reductions greater than the experimental scatter.

Fig.4 Force-Displacement Curve for Test of Fig.2

a) 30psi impact

b) 40psi impact

c) 60psi impact

Fig.5 C-Scans of All-Carbon Specimens

a) 40psi impact

b) 60psi impact

Fig.6 C-Scans of Hybrid Specimens

Fig.7 Normalised Residual Ply Strengths for All-Carbon and Hybrid Specimens

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

One of the principal aims of the present investigation was to develop a transverse impact test which allowed an unambiguous determination of the force, velocity and displacement history experienced by the specimen under different loading conditions. In practice two problems have arisen. In the first of these, while an accurate determination of velocity, and hence also displacement, at the centre of the specimen has been possible, see fig.2b, the particular arrangement of projectile and input bar has led to a series of steps in the displacement history which hinders the development of quasi-static equilibrium in the specimen and complicates the analysis leading to a load-displacement curve. More seriously, under loading conditions associated with the initiation of damage in, rather than the total failure of, the specimen, the Hopkinson-bar analysis for load has proved unsatisfactory and an alternative method, based on a quasi-static calibration of a back-surface strain gauge, has had to be used to estimate the applied load. For the present purpose this has allowed an approximate characterisation of the loading history in the various tests. In the longer term, however, modifications to the loading system will be required. In particular, by using a longer projectile it would be possible to maintain a near constant velocity and hence a displacement ramp for longer times and so eliminate the stepped displacement history from the early stages of the test.

Despite these problems distinct differences in the way damage develops under transverse impact loading between the all-carbon and the carbon/glass hybrid laminates have been observed. At 40psi, i.e. an impact velocity of $\sim 6\text{m/s}$, the hybrid specimen shows negligible fibre damage and only a small area of delamination. Whether this is at a carbon/glass or a glass/glass interface and its position with respect to the rear surface remains to be determined. At the same impact velocity the all-carbon specimen shows considerable fibre damage and a markedly greater area of delamination. At 60psi, i.e. an impact velocity of $\sim 8.3\text{m/s}$, the hybrid specimen shows a much greater area of delamination but fibre damage is still very limited whereas in the all-carbon specimen fibre fracture clearly predominates as the mechanism for absorbing impact damage.

Although these are only preliminary results and much more needs to be done before a detailed description of the impact response is possible and before firm conclusions can be drawn, the present results do suggest that when woven glass plies are added to an all-carbon laminate the principal energy absorbing mechanism for transverse impact loading changes from one associated with fibre fracture to one associated with delamination.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Grateful acknowledgment is made to Dr. G. Dorey and the Royal Aircraft Establishment for the use of their C-scan equipment, to the Science and Engineering Research Council for the award of a Research Assistantship (RKYL) and to the Air Force Office of Scientific Research, Air Force Systems Command, USAF, for financial support under Grant No. AFOSR-85-0218.

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